

Recommendations on improving the value of bioblitzes for science, engagement and learning

In support of researchers considering using the bioblitz method we have listed a number of recommendations below that may help get maximum benefit from the bioblitz. We also direct people to the Guide to running a BioBlitz, by Robinson et al. (2013).

Recommendations on improving the usefulness of data from bioblitzes

- consider whether a bioblitz is well suited to collect the data you need or to reach the audience you are aiming at
- specify the aims of your bioblitz
- recognize the limitations of a bioblitz as a scientific methodology
- define the target audience of your bioblitz (participation goals)
- define data collection goals
- document basic bioblitz information (e.g. aim, location, duration, number of participants, number of species recorded) - Keep it simple, but try to standardize the area and timeframe to improve repeatability
- gather basic demographic data on participants (age, gender, group)
- document results and learning outcomes
- plan the path for a societal impact (output -> outcome -> impact)

Recommendations on managing data from bioblitzes

- Prepare a data management plan for bioblitz data (Groom et al. 2017a).
- Publish data openly, make them findable and accessible (Kelling et al. 2019)
- Publish data along with the metadata that describes main features of the bioblitz (recording platforms can accommodate for this) (Nicolai et al., 2020)
- Use common platforms for the collection of data (use established data systems) (August et al. 2015)
- Make data findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable (FAIR, Wilkinson et al. 2016)
- Licence the data openly (Groom et al. 2017b)
- Define a data quality control system (data validation) (Wiggins et al. 2011, August et al. 2015)
- Tailor for event based datasets on [GBIF](#) (Postles and Bartlett, 2018)
- Consider novel technologies to improve survey quality, learning and participant experience (August et al. 2015)

Recommendations on evaluating bioblitz outcomes/impact

- Prepare an evaluation plan
- SMARTly define KPIs for your bioblitz
- Evaluate learning outcomes (guidance) - learning is an important motivator for participation

Recommendations to improve engagement through bioblitzes

- Forward plan feedback strategies to participants and dissemination of outcomes
- Prepare a communications strategy/plan
- Think of a simple message to communicate (television, radio and social media are important elements of a communication strategy)
- Feel free to name your bioblitz something else than 'bioblitz' if it sounds more familiar to your target audience e.g.: Bush Blitz project (Mesaglio and Callaghan 2021), Ocean Sampling Day (Kopf et al. 2015), Ecological Quick Check or 生態速查 (Martin and Marris 2017).
- Build connections between scientists and local communities
- Start planning well in advance
- Engage organisations and professionals
- Create a sense of community
- Consider ethics
- Think of strategies to increase inclusivity of bioblitzes

Recommendations to provide opportunities for your whole demographic

- Be conscious of parallel events that might attract your demographic or religious holidays that might refrain religious groups of people to participate in the bioblitz
- Locate the bioblitz in places accessible to public transport
- Choose sites that are easy to walk around
- Provide multiple ways to submit data (apps, paper, photographs)
- Games for children
- Prizes